
BALANCING FAMILY DYNAMICS AND CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN FAMILY-OWNED ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

In today's world corporate governance has become of significant importance but what isn't been given equal importance is that of Family governance. In family-owned enterprises, managing the two i.e., corporate governance and family governance can become a task, so, in order to ensure a well-organized business structure enterprises need to maintain a significant amount of balance between the two.

I. INTRODUCTION

Family and corporate governance are two of the most important aspects of any family-owned business enterprise. To understand this in a simpler way, we need to first understand what corporate governance is how does presence of family in a business affect it. Corporate governance is a set of rules and norms by which a company is directed and a business which is run by a family mainly influences the decisions to be taken in an enterprise. These types of enterprises constitute around 90% of total global enterprises. Family businesses are usually run on two principles; firstly it runs on rules and principles and secondly it runs on feelings and behaviour².

II. BALANCE BETWEEN THE TWO: CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND FAMILY GOVERNANCE

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² The Rawat Magazine ,The two pillars of governance, Understanding family business relationships, Issue 11 2011, <https://www.tharawat-magazine.com/understanding-family-business-relationships/>

Family-owned enterprises are such that are majorly run by the members of a family. Now, a very basic but intriguing question is that what actually comprises of a family? Who is involved in this definition of family? A family includes different business roles between husband and wife, parents and children, extended family, relatives and multiple generations. Family members usually have a stronger bond between themselves than with the employees which becomes a tedious task for employees as they are not able to match up to that level. In today's time, it's a very dominant factor to maintain a work-life balance not only for persons who work in family-owned enterprises but also for those persons who do not work in these types of enterprises. To maintain a significant amount of balance between corporate governance and family governance a certain things should be kept in mind, the first and foremost thing to be given consideration is to ensure that the employees are comfortable to work in an environment where a business is owned by a family. It is necessary to do this as there should not be any bias towards any family member in the eyes of an employee. Another thing to be given focus on is that no family member in an enterprise should hesitate in hiring someone who has more expertise in a particular field than a family member. In such a firm, communication is key, without communicating their needs, wants or expectations things won't be able to be in a free flow. One of the few things that should also be incorporated by family owned business enterprises is transparency, by doing so enterprises are creating a sense of security in the employees. All rules and regulations should be applicable to all in the firm, this ensures equality to all. The balance between corporate governance and family governance plays a major role in family-owned business enterprises.

III. CORPORATE GOVERNANCE

Corporate governance dates back to the 1970's which has gone through ample of changes ranging from post world war all the way till 2024³. The change went from the board of directors and shareholders being highly influenced by the managers to the organizations using technology to their advantage to protect themselves Earlier it used to be practised

³ The diligent team, Corporate governance history at a glance, What is the history of Corporate Governance and how has it changed?, March 18, 2024, <https://www.diligent.com/resources/blog/what-is-the-history-of-corporate-governance-and-how-has-it-changed>

worldwide but it didn't really have a term to it. The term "Corporate Governance" was first used in the United States and has been used ever since, worldwide. Earlier, many corporations were cheating the market place due to which strict codes were introduced in various places around the world. Few of the earliest codes were, the 1998 United Kingdom code, The 2000 India code, which was adopted by the Birla Committee, The 2002 United States and Australia code and the 2015 Japan code. By the introduction of these codes, corporate governance was given a new and defined meaning worldwide.

Corporate governance has numerous definitions such as academic definition, commission definition, practitioner definitions, legal definitions etc. One of the oldest definitions of corporate governance was given by Sir Adrian Cadbury in The Committee on the financial aspects of Corporate Governance, he defined corporate governance as, "The system by which companies are directed and controlled".

Corporate governance has evolved after going through enormous changes. Shareholders and stakeholders don't run the company but participate in its activities and the company is actually run by the directors. Corporate governance to date is evolving with time.

IV. CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN INDIA

In India, Corporate governance is very complex as there are various forms of business organizations which exist only in India. Good corporate governance ensures safety and security of the shareholders and managers in an organization. As India is very diverse in its organization types it has various regulatory frameworks, such as The Companies Act, 2013, the Securities and Exchange Board of India, Standard Listing Agreement of Stock Exchanges, Accounting standards issued by ICAI, Secretarial standards issued by ICSI⁴. These acts lay down a set of principles to be followed in order to maintain a good level of corporate governance. In 1999, India's first National Code on Corporate Governance was implemented by the Kumar Mangalam Committee.

The corporate governance guidelines in India have evolved since 1998 due to the efforts put in by several committees and the Ministry of Corporate Affairs.

⁴ Priyanshi8871, Regulatory Framework for Corporate governance in India, Corporate Governance in India, <https://www.legalserviceindia.com/legal/article-7435-corporate-governance-in-india.html>

V. FAMILY GOVERNANCE

Family governance is the process by which families create and improve their relationship with the enterprise. Family governance helps to set boundaries in a firm between family members and the enterprise itself. According to me, family governance is way different from corporate governance as corporate governance deals with the firm and is constant across firms but family governance deals with emotions and emotions cannot be compared to anything nor it can expect or be constant. Family governance is very complicated as its not defined anywhere nor explained, its just certain norms that are followed which are given the term family governance. There are certain things that crosses a person's mind while being involved in family governance some of which would be, how would family and corporate governance be practiced simultaneously? how would conflict be dealt with? how would family values be preserved? etc. Many of such questions would arise in a person's mind. Although combining family and business is complicated in nature, it is surprising how these businesses turn out as they have their positives and negatives.

Family governance in India

Indian civilization, culture, and customs are directly reflected in the way Indian families are run. Indian family companies adhere to unwritten codes of conduct that have been passed down through the generations. Meritocracy and aptitude are frequently subordinated to tradition and hierarchy.

Western cultures and businesses, on the other hand, are often considered to be more pragmatic in their approach; these enterprises are characterized by a genuine meritocracy and are propelled by entrepreneurial talent and personal desire. In a Western setting, creativity and improvisation are valued highly, but in Indian families, tradition and blind obedience to existing norms rule the day. Change happens slowly. Regardless of fitness or competency, and often even at the expense of a more capable successor, the eldest son in India typically inherits the family business. Contrarily, family-owned enterprises are uncommon in the western model above a particular scale and size, particularly those in which the founder family retains a sizable interest and influence.

In India, smaller enterprises typically end up in the hands of the wealthier children. It is commonplace for the parent to "sell" his company to his successor in order to receive favorable tax benefits. Moreover, it is highly typical for the entire founding family to be employed by the company; in contrast, proprietors in the West are more likely to leave the business in the hands of qualified managers.

The epic Mahabharata can be used to understand the influence of culture on the patriarchal attitude of India. In the Mahabharata, during the Kurukshetra War, Dhritarashtra is the King of the ancient Indian city of Hastinapur. Although he claims to want his nephews to succeed, he really wants his own children to succeed, and this portrays him as a hypocrite. Does this sound familiar? There's no denying that several patriarchs of well-known Indian business dynasties continue to harbor certain misconceptions about Dhritarashtra's character and disposition. It may begin as a natural love and affection, but with time it causes people to become legally blind.

VI. LIST OF FAMILY-OWNED BUSINESS ENTERPRISES

1. Reliance Industries

Reliance Industries was founded in 1966 by none other than Dhirubhai Ambani as a modest textile producer. Today, it ranks among the largest companies in the nation. They appear to be linked to the development of contemporary India. Reliance became this enormous company under Dhirubhai Ambani and later his sons, Mukesh and Anil Ambani. They are involved in petrochemicals, refining, oil, and telecommunications, among other things. They are currently among the biggest and wealthiest businesses in India. They have already raised an incredible 200 billion rupees (about \$2.40 billion) through bonds as of November 2023.

2. Tata Group

The Tata Group, which has been around since 1868, is more akin to the brightest point in Indian business. The creator, Jamsetji Tata, really got things started. Their

involvement in steel, hydropower, hospitality, and aviation has been crucial to India's development. India's industrial revolution was sparked in part by a textile mill. The succeeding generations simply kept moving into new territories. For example, in 1907, Tata Steel became the first integrated steel business in Asia. Subsequently, the 2007 Corus acquisition showcased India's economic expansion. Not to mention that in 2008, Tata Motors acquired Jaguar and Land Rover. One of the group's companies, Tata Consultancy Services, has encountered some legal issues in the US.

3. Wipro

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4. The TVS group

It's amazing to think that the TVS Group was founded in 1911. These days, it's a global giant that affects everything from electronics to autos and finance. That is currently one of the most well-known brands in the nation's automotive industry. Founded in 1978, they are not merely another participant in the motorbike industry; in fact, they are the third wealthiest in India. They are the nation's second-largest bike exporter, having shipped their two-wheelers to more than 60 nations. Yes, it all started in 1962 when Sundaram Clayton started working with auto parts. Then, the first two-seater moped in India, the TVS 50, made its debut in 1980.

5. Aditya Birla Group

In 1857, this group was founded, owing to G.D. Birla. This organization has expanded internationally, working in 36 nations on six continents. They have an interest in everything, including textiles, cement, and metals. However, their fame extends beyond India; they are a major force in the global arena. According to Forbes, by 2023, we're talking about an astounding \$65 billion. Leading the way is Kumar Mangalam Birla, accompanied by his family, Rajashree Birla, his mother, who is very involved in the group's charitable endeavors. Their commitment to giving back is demonstrated by the Aditya Birla Centre for Community Initiatives and Rural Development, which is spearheading their CSR efforts and having a significant impact under Rajashree Birla's direction.

VII. CHALLENGES IN FAMILY-OWNED BUSINESS ENTERPRISES

There are multiple challenges faced by a family when they are a firm, some of them are:

1. **Disputes within the Family:** The primary factors influencing the normal running of a family business are the emotional, financial, and physical problems among family members. At its foundation, family disputes are yet another factor that ruins a family business. Sibling rivalry, marital disagreements, and hatred between generations can all lead to this kind of family strife. Sadly, there isn't a right way to settle arguments like these within the family.
2. **Reluctance to Hire Outside Executives:** In most cases, family businesses give priority to members of their own family when filling high-level executive roles, especially in the early years. On the other hand, hiring an outsider becomes imperative if the company is going through a crisis. However, it's possible that new personnel from outside the family would require more training, which will cost more money and effort. Additionally, educating outside workers could have an impact on the company's production.
3. **Lack of Innovative Ideas:** When it comes to adopting cutting-edge technologies or novel ideas, family firms typically move more slowly than larger corporations. Family members are rarely excited about bringing novel ideas and cutting edge

techniques. Even though there might have been this kind of rigidity in the past, any organization with inadequate infrastructure and no creative plans would not last in the modern economic world.

4. Inadequate Long-Term Planning: Occasionally, first and second generations adopt a company model that works well and is regarded as a guide. Future generations are raised with this model and find it difficult to plan or visualize adjustments when they are needed. Every business sector, in general, needs to make modifications over time in order to overcome market conditions and grow gradually, or else they may encounter a variety of issues.

VIII. HOW CHALLENGES CAN BE MANAGED?

Establishing Boundaries: Indian family businesses that enjoy success are adept at establishing the boundaries that are necessary to achieve and maintain success. It is imperative to maintain a strict division between work and family problems as a general rule. Put another way, you should leave work at the workplace and keep family matters out of the way. You may concurrently keep your family and business in the proper balance by doing this.

Treat Workers Like Family: Successful family-run businesses treat all of their customers the same, whether or not they live in the same home. This practice occasionally includes customers as well. Employees will feel appreciated and well-cared for in organizations that treat them with the same family-like regard and affection. It's also crucial that none of the people connected to your family business show favoritism.

Effective Communication: Families develop their own communication style, so members may have different ideas and viewpoints. Therefore, listen to your family members without passing judgment and regard their opinions with respect rather than agreeing. As soon as there's a communication breakdown, close it. Also, seek the advice of an outside specialist if the problem is significant.

Practice Effective Governance: Establishing boundaries not only helps family-run businesses maintain better governance, but it also helps to keep work and family apart. Leaders from outside the family must associate for good governance to occur. It therefore takes the form of a non-family advisory, professional, or supervisory board with fewer family representatives. In this manner, efficient governance will enable your family business to grow.

IX. TIPS TO BALANCE FAMILY BUSINESS

- When our family provide us with love, care, and tolerance, we are sustained. Families, though, can sometimes exacerbate stressful work environments. Establish core principles, such as putting family first and spending quality time with them, in order to handle conflicting values in family-owned enterprises.
- Clearly define your basic principles and find the ideals that both your personal and professional life share. Make sure your expectations for your lifestyle and the reason you are in business are clear. Encourage family members to have frank conversations in order to establish a common goal, set of principles, and expectations for how time is spent and prioritized between work and family.
- Disagreement is inevitable in business, but it doesn't have to be allowed to be shaped by dysfunctional family relationships or antiquated generational communication standards. Team members and family business partners will gain from proactive conversations and agreement on what to do and don't do when disagreements arise.
- To identify areas where personal values overlap or clash, I would start by having a values exercise with every family member. It is essential that family members are aware of one another's positions
- Constant business interference with family time is one issue that family business owners may face. Family business owners that are successful establish boundaries.

Let Individuals Grow Into Their Passion You cannot inherit passion! Typically, what I see in family businesses is varying degrees of passion, which leads to misalignment that spills over into personal relationships. All members must be allowed to individually create and grow through struggle and crisis,

X. CONCLUSION

Families that create and uphold effective family governance can reap immeasurable benefits, including chances to improve communication, lessen conflict, educate the next generation, protect the family legacy, maintain family capital, and develop future family leaders. In the end, family peace, personal well-being, and financial success in a family-owned business depend on striking a balance between family and business objectives. A comprehensive strategy that takes into account both family and company factors is necessary to maintain a healthy work-life balance in a family firm. In a family business, communication, delegating, priority, and seeking outside counsel are critical to achieving a healthy work-life balance. On the other hand, family-owned enterprises offer distinct characteristics like sentimental attachment, familial connections, succession planning, and an extended viewpoint.

